

pH-metric studies on formation constants of the complexes of substituted thiazolyl Schiff's bases with some lanthanide metal ions

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Manuscript received 22 September 2011, revised 08 February 2012, accepted 09 February 2012

Abstract : The stability constants of the complexes of La^{III}, Pr^{III} and Sm^{III} with 2-[3-(4-methoxy-phenyl)-1-(4-phenyl-thiazol-2-ylimino)-allyl]-4-methylphenol, 2-[3-phenyl-1-(4-phenyl-thiazol-2-ylimino)-allyl]-4-methyl-phenol and 2-[3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-(4-phenyl-thiazol-2-ylimino)-allyl]-4-methyl-phenol have been determined by the pH-metric method in media of 70% dioxane-water mixture, 70% ethanol-water mixture and 70% acetone-water mixture at 0.1 M ionic strength and at (30 ± 0.1) °C temperature.

Keywords : pH-metric study, thiazolyl substituted Schiff's bases, La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Sm^{III}, metal-ligand stability constants.

Introduction

Rossotti and Rossoti have defined complex as a species formed by association of two or more simple species each capable of independent existence. When one of the species is metal ion, resulting entity is metal complex. The ligands are attached to metal atom in such a manner to form heterocyclic ring. The extensive work in coordination complexes has been made possible with the help of number of experimental techniques. Metal ligand stability constant determination has wide significance in different fields of physical chemistry, medicinal chemistry and thermochemistry.

The study of coordination compounds specifically the metal complexes containing thiazole based ligand is of much interest due to their importance in various chemical and biological systems. Literature survey reveals that the thiazole nucleus is the centre of attraction in developing various chemical entities of biological interest^{1,2}. Thiazole derivatives³ containing N=C=S moiety have been employed as antiphycoctics, antimalarial⁴, antibacterial and antiinflammatory⁵. Thiazole substituted compounds plays a vital role in pharmaceutical practice due to their wide range of biological activities⁶⁻⁸ like fungicidal⁹, insecticidal¹⁰ and anthelmintic activities and also known for their pharmacological activity¹¹. A perusal of literature has revealed that Schiff's bases belongs to a widely used group of organic intermediates, important for production

of specialty chemicals such as pharmaceuticals, rubber additives and as aminoprotective groups in organic synthesis.

The studies on complex formation by tripositive rare-earth metal ions with biologically important ligands are in progress because of their role in biological process¹².

Amrallah and Haty¹³ have studied the stability constants of ternary metal complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} with amino acids using ethanol-water mixture as a medium at 0.1 M ionic strength. Akuskar and Swami¹⁴ have discussed the proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constant of Cu^{II} with 3-chloro-2-hydroxy propiophenone at 0.1 M ionic strength in 60% ethanol-water mixture. They studied the effect of ligand basicity and metal ions on the stability and also the relation $\log K = apK + b$ was tested. Doshi and Pawar¹⁵ has studied the interaction of Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Fe^{III}, Al^{III} and Nd^{III} with isoxazolines. They showed the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes in the pH range at about 2-9 in 70% dioxane-water mixture.

Talebi and Semnani¹⁶ have studied the interaction between silver ions and several crown ethers in different acetonitrile-water mixtures. They determined the formation constants of resulting 1 : 1 complexes.

Narwade and Naik¹⁷ discussed the stability constants of the complexes of substituted pyrazole with lanthanide metal ions such as Dy^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III} and Tb^{III} and also explains the influence of ionic strength on complex equilibrium in a 70% dioxane-water mixture.

The present paper reports pH-metric studies on the interaction of rare earth metal ions La^{III} , Pr^{III} and Sm^{III} with 2-[3-(4-methoxy-phenyl)-1-(4-phenyl-thiazol-2-yl-imino)-allyl]-4-methyl-phenol (L^1), 2-[3-phenyl-1-(4-phenyl-thiazol-2-ylimino)-allyl]-4-methyl-phenol (L^2) and 2-[3-(4-chloro-phenyl)-1-(4-phenyl-thiazol-2-ylimino)-allyl]-4-methyl-phenol (L^3) in 1 : 1 ratio at 30 ± 0.1 °C. For this study 70% dioxane-water mixture, 70% ethanol-water mixture and 70% acetone-water mixture were used as solvent. The ionic strength was maintained constant at 0.1 M. The proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants were calculated by pointwise calculation method and half integral method.

where R = H, OCH_3 and Cl

Experimental

Materials and solutions :

The microwave irradiation was used for the synthesis of the ligands. Purity was verified by analytical and spectral study i.e. melting point determination, IR and NMR spectra. The stock solution of the ligands (0.01 M) were prepared by dissolving the required amount of the ligands in a minimum volume of 70% dioxane-water mixture, 70% ethanol-water mixture and 70% acetone-water mixture. 0.01 M metal solutions were prepared by dissolving the requisite quantities in distilled water. The concentrations of metal ions were estimated by titrating against disodium salt of EDTA solution by procedure of Schwarzenbach¹⁸. The standard NaOH solution was prepared by Vogel's method¹⁹.

Apparatus and procedure :

The pH of the solutions was measured with a EQUIPTRONICS micro controller pH meter (Model EQ-621) equipped with a combined electrode and magnetic stirrer. The instrument was calibrated before each titration with an aqueous standard buffer solution of pH 4, 7

and 9 prepared from Qualigens buffer tablets. All the weighings were done on electronic balance [ConTech CB-Series with accuracy ± 0.001].

The following titrations were carried out pH metrically. (i) Acid titration, (ii) Acid + ligand titration and (iii) Acid + ligand + metal titration.

Ionic strength 0.1 M was maintained by using HNO_3 and KNO_3 solutions. The titrations were carried out by using Calvin-Bjerrum pH metric titration technique^{20,21}. The same techniques were applied for 70% ethanol-water mixture and 70% acetone-water mixture. The total volume of each system was made up to 25 ml. The proton-ligand stability constants were calculated from the pH values obtained from the titrations using the Irving-Rossotti method²² was mentioned in Table 1.

Table 1. Proton ligand stability constants (pK) of ligand L^1 to L^3 at 0.1 M ionic strength and at (30 ± 0.1) °C temperature

Medium	Ligand	pK	
		Half integral method	Pointwise calculation method
Ethanol-water	L^1	4.25	4.06
Acetone-water		4.60	4.6
Dioxane-water		3.10	3.5
Ethanol-water	L^2	4.80	5.10
Acetone-water		4.20	4.10
Dioxane-water		3.60	3.66
Ethanol-water	L^3	5.8	5.8
Acetone-water		5.7	5.4
Dioxane-water		5.7	5.8

Results and discussion

The ligands L^1 , L^2 and L^3 used in the present investigation contains only one dissociable proton from hydroxyl group. In general ligands can be represented as HL and dissociated as,

$$K' = \frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{L}^-]}{[\text{HL}]}$$

The proton-ligand formation number \bar{n}_A was calculated by Irving-Rossotti expression. The proton ligand stability constant pK were calculated from formation curves by pointwise calculation method and half integral method. From formation curves drawn from \bar{n}_A vs pH (half integral method) by noting pH at which $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$ shown in

Fig. 1. The accurate values of pK were determined by pointwise calculation method. The \bar{n}_A values were calculated with the help of following eq. (1).

$$\bar{n}_A = \gamma - \left[\frac{(E^0 + N)(V_2 - V_1)}{(V_0 + V_1)T^0_L} \right] \quad (1)$$

$$\bar{n} = \left[\frac{(E^0 + N)(V_3 - V_2)}{(V_0 + V_2)T^0_m} \right] \quad (2)$$

where γ is number of dissociable proton, N is concentration of NaOH (0.1 mol dm^{-3}), E^0 is resultant concentration of acid, T^0_L is resultant concentration of ligand, V^0 is initial volume of the reaction mixture, V_1 and V_2 are volume of alkali added in acid, ligand titration and metal titration and T^0_m is concentration of the metal ion in the reaction mixture.

Fig. 1. pH against volume of 0.10 mol dm^{-3} NaOH at $I = 0.1 \text{ M}$ at $(30 \pm 0.1) \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; (1) = acid curve, (2), (3) and (4) are the curves of ligands L^1 , L^2 and L^3 .

Similarly metal ligand formation number \bar{n} values was calculated by using eq. (2) and metal-ligand stability constants were determined from formation curves by pointwise calculation method and half integral method mentioned in Table 2.

During titration process there is a colour change of solution. In La^{III} titration colour becomes off white or yellowish. For Pr^{III} , light green colour of solution gets darken and for Sm^{III} colour changes from yellow to orange. This colour change during titration confirms 1 : 1

Table 2. Metal-ligand stability constants of complexes La^{III} , Pr^{III} and Sm^{III} with ligand L^1 , L^2 and L^3 in 70% dioxane-water, 70% acetone-water and 70% ethanol-water medium

Medium	System	Constants	Method	
			Half integral	Pointwise calculation
70% Ethanol-water	$\text{La}^{\text{III}}\text{-L}^1$	$\log K_1$	4.5	4.38
		$\log K_2$	7.10	7.26
	$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}}\text{-L}^1$	$\log K_1$	3.20	3.30
		$\log K_2$	6.0	5.72
	$\text{Sm}^{\text{III}}\text{-L}^1$	$\log K_1$	3.5	3.30
		$\log K_2$	5.7	5.72
70% Acetone-water	$\text{La}^{\text{III}}\text{-L}^1$	$\log K_1$	4.5	4.45
		$\log K_2$	9.7	9.2
	$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}}\text{-L}^1$	$\log K_1$	4.0	3.5
		$\log K_2$	8.4	7.9
	$\text{Sm}^{\text{III}}\text{-L}^1$	$\log K_1$	3.60	3.44
		$\log K_2$	7.60	6.96
70% Dioxane-water	$\text{La}^{\text{III}}\text{-L}^1$	$\log K_1$	1.40	2.91
		$\log K_2$	5.05	4.95
	$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}}\text{-L}^1$	$\log K_1$	2.95	3.17
		$\log K_2$	4.20	3.78
	$\text{Sm}^{\text{III}}\text{-L}^1$	$\log K_1$	2.60	2.32
		$\log K_2$	4.30	4.18
70% Ethanol-water	$\text{La}^{\text{III}}\text{-L}^2$	$\log K_1$	3.5	4.85
		$\log K_2$	6.60	7.94
	$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}}\text{-L}^2$	$\log K_1$	3.05	3.89
		$\log K_2$	5.5	7.13
	$\text{Sm}^{\text{III}}\text{-L}^2$	$\log K_1$	3.10	3.410
		$\log K_2$	8.80	7.066
70% Acetone-water	$\text{La}^{\text{III}}\text{-L}^2$	$\log K_1$	4.4	3.99
		$\log K_2$	8.3	7.057
	$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}}\text{-L}^2$	$\log K_1$	4.3	3.178
		$\log K_2$	7.3	7.759
	$\text{Sm}^{\text{III}}\text{-L}^2$	$\log K_1$	3.8	4.039
		$\log K_2$	7.3	8.590
70% Dioxane-water	$\text{La}^{\text{III}}\text{-L}^2$	$\log K_1$	2.9	3.2
		$\log K_2$	5.9	6.57
	$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}}\text{-L}^2$	$\log K_1$	3.0	3.6
		$\log K_2$	7.0	6.47
	$\text{Sm}^{\text{III}}\text{-L}^2$	$\log K_1$	2.90	3.762
		$\log K_2$	7.05	6.822
70% Ethanol-water	$\text{La}^{\text{III}}\text{-L}^3$	$\log K_1$	5.5	5.53
		$\log K_2$	8.9	8.9
	$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}}\text{-L}^3$	$\log K_1$	4.5	4.5
		$\log K_2$	8.1	7.9
	$\text{Sm}^{\text{III}}\text{-L}^3$	$\log K_1$	5.2	4.6
		$\log K_2$	8.30	8.26

Table-2 (contd.)

70% Acetone-water	La ^{III} -L ³	log K ₁	5.6	5.54
		log K ₂	10.2	9.47
	Pr ^{III} -L ³	log K ₁	4.40	4.9
		log K ₂	8.3	8.36
	Sm ^{III} -L ³	log K ₁	5.2	5.8
		log K ₂	9.1	8.96
70% Dioxane-water	La ^{III} -L ³	log K ₁	4.10	4.49
		log K ₂	10.30	8.65
	Pr ^{III} -L ³	log K ₁	5.10	4.68
		log K ₂	8.10	8.31
	Sm ^{III} -L ³	log K ₁	5.0	8.27
		log K ₂	9.10	9.57

Fig. 2. pH against volume of 0.10 mol dm⁻³ NaOH at $I = 0.1 M$ at $(30 \pm 0.1) ^\circ C$; (1) = ligand curve, (2), (3) and (4) are metal curves of La^{III}, Pr^{III} and Sm^{III} respectively.

complex formation due to replaceable H⁺ from -OH group. Due to formation of coordination bond at N site, there is formation of 1 : 2 complex.

The deviation of metal titration curve from ligand curve commenced from pH 2.7 for La, pH 2.6 for Pr and pH 2.9 for Sm. The significant departure of ligand curve from acid curve indicates chelate formation between metal ion and ligand gets confirmed. As solutions used are very dilute possibility of formation of polynuclear species is very less.

There is no specific trend in proton-ligand stability constant. This is due to variation in polar nature of solvents and solvent-solvent interactions.

In the present investigation there is no specific trend in metal-ligand stability constants as in Table 2. This may

be due to the fact that (i) difference in redox potentials E^0 values of La, Pr and Sm is very less. Hence though they have strong tendency to lose electron and undergo oxidation, the reducing power of La, Pr and Sm differs to very less extent, (ii) for trivalent lanthanide ions, increase in ionic size, increases the stability of complexes²². This is due to lanthanide contraction²³. But the variation in results may be due to metal solvent interactions.

Conclusion :

From the data presented in Table 2, it can be concluded that there is stepwise complex formation between trivalent lanthanide ions and thiazolyl substituted Schiff's bases. From the stability constants of complexes it can be concluded that for trivalent lanthanide metal ions basicity decreases with decrease in ionic radius. This results in decrease in complexes formation tendency in case of hydrated ions.

The metal-ligand stability constant has significance in determination of thermodynamic parameter in thermochemistry.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to the Principal, Shri Shivaji Science College, Amravati for providing necessary facilities while investigating the present work.

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Note

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